

Establishing Medical Centre in Wildlife Parks: A Case of Murchison Falls National Park, Uganda

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ABSTRACT

For years, Murchison Falls National Park, Uganda experiences a variety of infectious diseases affecting both the humans and wildlife due to its tropical weather, wetlands and rich biodiversity. The significant diseases to be addressed are malaria spread by the breeding of the mosquitoes around the water bodies, sleeping sickness cause by tsetse fly vector spreading Trypanosoma, zoonotic disease-causing brucellosis leading to health risks among the wildlife and human in the park. In addition, the park region experiences fever that arises from unbearable illnesses such as typhoid fever, non-typhoidal, salmonellosis and influenza triggering body weaknesses, headaches, digestive and respiratory upsets associated with acute bacterial infections among the households adjacent to the park (Aruho, 2021). The study proposes the need for Medical Center in the park in case of any emergency like injuries and contagious diseases in the park (Aruho, 2021).

INTRODUCTION

Murchison Falls National Park is an oldest and well known for its waterfalls, rich biodiversity, abundant birds and other species such as lions, leopards, elephants, Cape buffaloes, Rothschild's giraffes, Jackson's hartebeest, bushbucks, hippos, warthogs, oribis, jackals, duikers, vervet monkeys and other categories. There are also crocodiles, variety of reptiles and amphibians making it a prominent place for safaris and bird watching in Uganda. The park's environment serves as a focal point for the transmittable disease in the area such as malaria fever caused by anopheles mosquito parasite thrived in stagnant water in some regions of the park, typhoid fever triggered by salmonella Typhi bacteria transmitted by fecal-oral routes through transmitted water in the park, sleeping sickness spread by tsetse fly, fevers of unknown origin and Zoonoses increased the health risks of humans, livestock and wildlife in the park. These diseases are brought about by buildup surface water, poor disposal of animal waste and inadequate sanitation infrastructure in the park. The people who experienced these diseases are the elderly tourists, oil miners, children, game rangers, drivers, households adjacent to the park and administrative staffs due to open air and increased contact with contaminated environment. So, there is a need to establish a

Medical Center in the park to help in case of emergency such as injuries and other infectious diseases (Kizza et al, 2021).

BACKGROUND OF THE STUDY

Murchison Falls National Park is the largest and oldest conservation area located in North-western Uganda at the Northern end of Albertine Rift Valley. The park covers 3, 840 square kilometers, spreading inland from lake Albert along the Victoria Nile to Karuma Falls. The park was authoritatively established under Uganda National Parks Act, developing from the existing game reserves. It became a leading safari in East Africa attracting over 60,000 visitors annually. In the last ten years, the park faced obstacles such as feverish infections across the households near the park with unbearable illnesses such as malaria fever, typhoid fever, non-typhoidal infections, salmonellosis, influenza and other health related complications that need urgent help (Uganda Wildlife authority, 2023-2024).

Problem Statement

The study establishes a need for medical center in Murchison Falls National Park. The Medical center is necessary for emergency response for critical conditions such as injuries, animal attack, snake bites, bee sting triggering allergy and other health concerns like malaria fever, typhoid fever bovine

trypanosomiasis and zoonotic infections for better treatment and prevention (Kizza, et al 2021).

Overall Objective

- To establish a medical Center through Health Management Information System that promote emergency in treatment of diseases, patient care, resource management and timely health intervention in the park (Murchison Falls Game Park Outreach Report, 2025).

Research Questions

1. How do Health Management Information Systems serve the community in the park?
2. How to design a Health Management Information System infrastructure within the park’s medical center to collect and manage patient data efficiently and accurately?
3. How to apply Management Information System to establish a medical center in the park?

Significance of the Study

Significance to the society: A Health management System performs important role in the modern society by establishing healthcare services to deliver, manage and improve accurate patient history that will help doctors and nurses offer faster and safer care to reduce medical errors for better results of individuals and communities.

Significance to the researchers: A Health management system that provides students with practical experience in managing digital health data and bridging the gap between theory and real-world health care practice. To offer valuable data for studying health trends, evaluating outcomes and advancing medical knowledge to support innovation, interdisciplinary learning and preparation for future healthcare leaders to be part of digital and data driven-world.

Health Management Information Systems serve the community in the park

Health Management Information Systems are integrated systems designed to collect, store, manage and transmit health-related data to support decision making in the delivery of health care (WHO, 2008). In the context of Murchison Falls National Park, this system serves the communities by promoting effective collection and analysis of health data to support monitoring of disease outbreak, handling the health care resources and enabling coordination among the healthcare providers. This contributes to improve the delivery of health services and the overall well-being of the communities living in and around the park (Uganda Ministry of Health, 2022).

Design a Health Management Information System infrastructure within the park’s medical center to collect and manage patient data efficiently and accurately

In Murchison Falls National Park, a Health Management Information System would be designed to capture the data of patient-level at the park’s medical center and transform the data into actionable understandings for health workers and managers of the park. These include registration, documentation, laboratory and pharmacy interfaces, reporting dashboards, data quality control and data secured measure. In the long-run, this will help detects the outbreaks and trend of diseases, track service utilization and outcomes, allocate resources effectively and coordinate health activities with surrounding communities. This contributes to better health outcomes for the park’s residents and visitors for the sustainability (Uganda Ministry of Health, 2022).

Applying Management Information System to establish a medical center in the park

To apply a health Management Information System in establishing a medical center within Murchison Falls National Park, the process involves numerous ways such as conduct a need assessment to understand the specific health data requirements and existing gaps and ensure resource availability in the park community. Design the infrastructure to include the registration of patient, clinical data documentation, laboratory and pharmacy interfaces, reporting modules based on the context of the park. Implement interoperable software solutions to ensure whole data flow and integration with Uganda’s national health systems. Equip the facility with security and privacy protocols to protect the information of the patient. Continuously, monitor, evaluate and improve the system to maintain effective health services delivery and support public health decision-making within the park (World Health organization, 2008).

METHODOLOGY

This study employs a descriptive cross-sectional strategy to examine the prevalence of diseases within Murchison Falls National Park using secondary data. The methodology involves the orderly collection and analysis of pre-existing data collected by several stakeholders over a stated period.

Data Collection Technique

Secondary data obtained from Veterinary Records, Wildlife Disease Surveillance Reports, Government Health Databases, Published Research Articles and reports from Conservation NGOs working within and around the park. These data consist of documented cases of infectious and parasitic diseases among wildlife, livestock and possibly human within the park environment.

Area of Study and Population

The study focuses on Murchison Falls National Park. The target population consist of humans, various speciefies of wildlife, livestock and adjacent communities in the park, made the data accessible.

RESEARCH FINDINGS

Medical Services at Murchison Falls National Park

There are nearby medical centers and hospitals outside the park such as, Masindi General Hospital, Hoima Regional Referral Hospital, Gulu Regional referral Hospital, Buliisa Health Centre IV, Pakwach Health Centre IV and Mubaku Community Medical Centre as the smaller centers around the region. However; these hospitals and medical centers are far away from the park and can't help in case of any emergency situation.

When visiting Murchison Falls National Park, the visitors are encouraged to carry with them Personal Medical Kits, Purchase Travel Insurance and inform the tour operator about some health concerns such as medication, allergies and chronic illnesses before the trip for further care. There are a number of challenges related to medical services at Murchison Falls National Park. These include lack of medical facilities in the park, long distance to hospitals and medical centers, poor infrastructure like roads and communication. Since there are nearby clinics to the park, they are not well-equipped for serious emergencies such as patients with critical issues, must be transferred to larger hospitals for further care. So, there are no medical center located inside the park to help in first aid supplies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Establishing a medical center in Murchison Falls National Park is a significant move toward enhancing healthcare access for both visitors and local communities. It would improve emergency response like injuries and infectious diseases, support wildlife protection efforts by facilitating veterinary care and encourage sustainable tourism by certifying the safety of the visitors. Such initiative not only addresses immediate health needs but also contributes to the long-term wellbeing and development of the region adjacent to the park. This project stands as a strategic investment in the park's future to balance human health and environmental preservation.

RECOMMENDATIONS

- Proposes a Medical Centre with integrated Health Management Information System within the park to help in emergency treatment of injuries and other infectious diseases among the administrative staffs, drivers, game wardens, tourists and staffs with blood pressure and diabetes, children, oil miners and communities adjacent to the park.

- Recommend visitors to carry personal medical kits, purchase travel insurance and inform the operator concerning health matters before the trip.

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